

Learning with Community: Developing Citizen-Led Housing

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Abstract

Creating a flourishing city and delivering the Sustainable Development Goals in urban development is a complex challenge because of the interconnectedness between the different goals as well as the diverse perspectives and prioritisation of values among stakeholders. To navigate through this complexity and effectively orchestrate changes at the scales needed, innovation programmes have to be co-produced by and with stakeholders. Effective co-production requires mindful leadership and skilful facilitation. We introduce a learning framework which helps innovators and change programme leaders to facilitate an integrated approach to stakeholder engagement, so they can lead their project effectively and stimulate desired, community-led transformation. We examine the conceptual underpinnings of the framework, drawing from evidence in the literature about motivation and decision theories, co-production, learning, and resilient agency. We then describe how this framework has been developed in a case study of a citizen-led housing project in Knowle West, Bristol, UK and how the solution developed responds to the urban challenge themes of the Urban ID project: mobility & accessibility, health & happiness, equality & inclusion, carbon-neutral city, and environment & ecology. We highlight the importance of framing co-production as a learning journey and the need for the effective facilitation of both the behavioural processes of getting things done and the learning facilitation processes which enable people to change their minds and behaviours. These lead to the argument that mindful leadership in both thought and action and the development of a collaborative learning infrastructure are important success factors for co-production in Living Labs.

Keywords: *citizen-led housing, urban diagnostics, learning infrastructure, stakeholder engagement*

1 Introduction

Creating a flourishing city and delivering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in urban development is a complex challenge which requires a holistic systems approach to diagnose problems, innovate solutions and sustain community directed change. This complexity is rooted in the inter-connectedness between the different goals as well as the diverse perspectives, disciplines, domains and prioritisation of values among stakeholders. To navigate through this complexity and effectively orchestrate changes at the scales needed, the change programme has to be co-produced by and with stakeholders so that there is a sustainable commitment from the people and groups who will be responsible for delivering it.

There is an established consensus manifested in the SDGs regarding what needs to be achieved. The pressing question is how we, as individuals, teams and organisations from all sectors and domains, can deliver these goals in a manner which is itself sustainable. From the authors' experience in working with stakeholders in the urban areas of Bristol and South Gloucestershire, we knew that many people and organisations are passionate and committed about leading positive change and have organically developed valuable assets, know-how and networked communities. We therefore aimed to understand whether, and what, barriers might exist that block this positive, organic energy for change from developing into authentic outcomes. This was the challenge of the UrbanID research project, which aimed to develop a framework to help stakeholders to take an integrated view on the issues or places of their concern and to surface, and then address, any systemic barriers.

In this paper, we first attend to the conceptual understanding that underpinned the development of the UrbanID framework, then turn the focus to the challenge and barriers encountered in community engagement, using the case study of a citizen-led housing project in Knowle West. We conclude by a reflexive analysis of lessons learned in the co-production process.

2 Urban Integrated Diagnostics and Stakeholder Engagement

The UrbanID project was one of the five Urban Living Partnership (ULP) pilots funded by Research Councils UK and Innovate UK to explore the transdisciplinary research challenges of future urban living. UrbanID aimed to create a novel Integrated Diagnostics framework and methods to address these interconnected urban challenges.

Whilst there was a serious commitment from stakeholders, the UrbanID project also recognised that there was a collective ‘business as usual’ mindset amongst a broader set of stakeholders in the city, which reinforced existing siloed practices and made it difficult to engage thematically across different domains, disciplines, and commercial and political interests. The ability to engage stakeholders in the development of a more user-centred and joined-up view was seen as a critical success factor for the delivery of the Sustainable Development Goals across the city.

The UrbanID framework was built upon three methodological components: systems thinking, learning design, and co-production methods. The project design was co-produced with a high degree of multi-stakeholder participation from the quadruple helix of public, private, voluntary and academic sector organisations across the City of Bristol and the South Gloucestershire local authority areas². To stimulate a holistic, user-led approach, five challenge themes were identified by the group:

- Mobility & accessibility;
- Health & happiness;
- Equality & inclusion;
- Carbon neutral city;
- Environment & ecology.

The UrbanID framework, as an analytical tool, focused on the challenge themes through the lens of authentic, user-led case studies, exploring how the challenges manifest themselves in the life- narratives of citizens, business, government, third sector, and academic actors and impact on wider ecological systems. The framework was developed and tested through five case studies, including two transportation infrastructure projects, two local neighbourhood areas projects, and a leadership organisation focused on environmental sustainability.

3 Learning Together to Co-produce

The emergence of co-production as a public service planning and delivery approach was primarily driven by the need for fiscal austerity. However, co-production has since been recognised as a more effective way to support citizens to achieve their wellbeing (Meijer, 2016; Nabatchi Tina, Sancino Alessandro, & Sicilia Mariafrancesca, 2017). Advocates of co-production believe that all stakeholders will participate and contribute from their particular viewpoints, drawing on their unique capabilities, if they can envision some value that they might gain from doing so. This belief is based on

² For more details about this project visit <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/cabot/research/urban-id/co.uk>

the assumptions that stakeholders can align around a shared goal, are motivated to work together and are open and ready to engage with relevant diverse perspectives, data, information and practices and to struggle together to find workable solutions. These assumptions call for a learning design approach because what is required is a way of facilitating or 'scaffolding' a process of learning together to solve complex problems when the target outcome is not known in advance (Bauman, 2001).

This process has at least six collective core tasks. Stakeholders need to:

- i) Align sufficiently around a shared purpose;
- ii) Analyse the problem and any 'blockers' to achieving that purpose;
- iii) Decide how to go about a change initiative that will achieve the purpose;
- iv) Identify what a good outcome would look like and how it might be measured;
- v) Select, collect, curate and re-structure relevant data and information into a new solution which achieves the purpose;
- vi) Deliver and evaluate the outcome.

These are key tasks of collaborative learning understood as a process, or a journey, which operates in authentic contexts, rather than in the 'training room' or the 'lecture theatre.' Co-production refers to the involvement of all stakeholders in the process: the learning design principles provide a 'context-neutral' way of moving beyond the Why and addressing the How of going about achieving a collaborative purpose.

4 Understanding Motivation and Engagement

Given that collaborative learning takes time and effort and, by definition, entails a deviation from business-as-usual, it depends significantly on stakeholders' motivation and willingness to engage in what is likely to be a disruptive process. A study of motivation to learn in a performance-oriented culture shows that motivation is influenced significantly by external factors in the immediate environment and the cultural context of the person who is learning. Furthermore, people's sense of agency, choice, identity and belief structures are four key mechanisms that drive deep engagement and achievement (Harlen & Deakin Crick, 2003; Sebba et al., 2008).

More general research into human motivation has linked people's behaviour to their (unmet) needs, which are understood to have a hierarchy (Maslow, 1943), as well as being wide ranging, from subsistence and protection to creation, identity and freedom (Max-Neef, Elizalde, & Hopenhayn, 1991). While the satisfaction of needs explains the motivation underpinning people's actions, *how* those needs are satisfied and the *extent* to which those needs have been satisfied are perceived differently from person to person. These perceptions inform a person's construction of their goals – their

internal representations of pathways leading towards a desired state (Austin & Vancouver, 1996). Goal constructs will recursively create a lens through which a person understands the world and the values they live by. This self-reinforcing process leads to the formation of a person's worldview over time and will have already shaped a person's identity, relationships and expectations in his or her social network by the time they encounter a community problem which they want to address collaboratively.

5 Engagement decisions in authentic contexts

Despite need satisfaction being a fundamental motivator, people do not generally make direct, or rational, choices about which need they are to satisfy next because needs are complex and interdependent and sometimes outside a person's awareness. The choice is made at a more visceral and practical level that concerns how a person deploys effort, time or resource. It is the consequences of a person's actions that will lead to the satisfaction or deprivation of needs, which means the behavioural choices are connected to needs in a many-to-many manner (Ballard, Yeo, Loft, Vancouver, & Neal, 2016).

In authentic, real-life contexts, as opposed to experimental settings or training rooms, people usually make decisions about their next best action amongst multiple options, each of which has consequences which relate to multiple needs. People do not have sufficient mental capacity to assess all the consequences of all possible actions systematically; they consider the consequences sequentially, one after another (Ballard et al., 2016), and do not always make deliberate choices but depend on intuition and routines (Betsch & Haberstroh, 2005; Marchiori, Adriaanse, & Ridder, 2017). Therefore, the attention a person gives to the consequence of a choice accounts for a significant part of a decision process, while the preferences underpinning a decision are rooted in agency, goal or belief constructs, and needs.

6 A layered framework of motivation

These motivation related factors and mechanisms can be grouped into at least four layers in an inside-outside model of motivation, in that the inside layers are more strongly driven by internal processes than external ones whilst the outer layers are more open to external influence factors (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Layers of sources of influence on participant's motivation to engage in Living Lab activities

Need Satisfaction represents an underpinning value system, which is largely a result of the co-evolution of the human species. Fundamental human needs are qualitatively stable and broadly similar across populations, but need satisfaction is subject to cultural influences and will be assessed subjectively with reference to the extent and ways in which needs are satisfied in a specific time and place (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Most human moral judgements have also been incorporated into our basic psychology (Greene, 2014) and therefore it is reasonable to consider “value” as an integrated part of the complex system of human needs (Pink, 2011).

Goal Construct is a person’s internal cognitive, affective and volitional model of how the world works and thus how a person can satisfy his or her needs. Hence, goal constructs imply at least two sets of knowledge relating to needs: i) declarative knowledge which characterises what is needed and the options available, and ii) procedural knowledge about the set of actions that constitute an option. Even though people have similar set of needs, they assign differing weights of importance to those needs and have differing understandings of the options for achieving satisfaction.

Agency is the capability of a person to utilise the structure of a system to achieve his or her goal (Giddens, 1984). As far as motivation is concerned, it is the person’s belief in whether he or she has agency that influences the person’s decision to engage with a goal. There are two agency-related beliefs: self-belief that the person can act him or herself, and belief and trust in the agents the person needs to work with in order to act and achieve a goal. Even though a person may over or under estimate his or her

actual agency, their agentic belief will strengthen their actual agency and the increase of actual agency will strengthen their belief.

Framing is the interpretation of the relationships the person has with other people, the material environment and their social context, which informs the person's attention and temporal importance weighting of goals (Ballard et al., 2016). To give an example, Steele (2011) describes how female students feel the pressure to prove their abilities in solving difficult maths problems because there is a stereotype cultural belief that female students are less able in maths than their male peers. Alternative task framing can remove the identity threat and nudge the students to attend to the goal of, say, stretching their ability in solving difficult math problems, instead of proving wrong the stereotype about their maths ability (Steele, 2011).

7 The learning framework of UrbanID

Framing co-production activities as learning opportunities is of critical importance to overcome the siloed and fragmented thinking and practices embedded in stakeholders' business-as-usual modes of operation. This is because doing something differently, by definition, involves learning. If we already know what to do, we don't need to learn and 'business-as-usual-practices' will be the default *modus operandi*. However, innovation and change require moving into the unknown and this involves learning. To approach new learning opportunities (i.e. change) productively requires learning power, which is 'the relational and embodied process through which we regulate the flow of energy and information over time' in pursuit of a purpose (Deakin Crick, Huang, Ahmed Shafi, & Goldspink, 2015, p. 121). Eight dimensions of learning power emerged from five studies with more than 50,000 cases: Mindful Agency; Hope and Optimism, Sense-Making, Creativity, Curiosity, Belonging, Collaboration and Openness to Learning. These are malleable qualities which emerge from the interactions between the learner and their environment (*ibid.*). Learning power is influenced by relationships and social culture – the data suggests that where a culture is characterised by trust, affirmation and challenge then people are more likely to move into new ways of thinking and acting, mobilising their learning power in pursuit of their goal (Deakin Crick & Joldersma, 2007; Deakin Crick, McCombs, Haddon, Broadfoot, & Tew, 2007). The implication of this for a Living Lab is that when activities are designed in a way that enable people to utilise and develop their learning power e.g. creativity, curiosity, mindful agency, sustainable learning relationships etc, it will not only help people learn better together but it also incentivises future participation and goal achievement.

The layered framework of motivation clarifies the depth of influence required for

significant behavioural change at scale within a community and highlights the importance of learning design in stakeholders' engagement in change and innovation. Substantive change occurs when a person's understanding of their needs and their worldview is modified, and when they have formed sufficient agency to pursue a new goal; and a person's agency and goal constructs change only through learning.

This layered framework of motivation, the tasks of collaborative learning, and holistic systems thinking constitute the *learning framework* of UrbanID. In the following sections we describe how the framework was developed and applied through a particular UrbanID case study focused on citizen-led housing development.

8 We Can Make: The Citizen-Led Housing Project

Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC) is an arts centre, founded in 1996 and rooted in the community of Knowle West, Bristol, UK. KWMC works across different disciplines using art and technology to address issues including health, housing, and smart cities. KWMC runs Bristol Living Lab and as such fosters civic innovation by collaborating with residents, artists, local authorities, business and academia to support people to make positive change and explore new ways of living better together.

The *We Can Make* project is a response to community demands and concerns about housing need in the area. The project team carried out extensive participative research in Knowle West, a housing estate on the outskirts of Bristol consisting of 5,500 households and 12,000 residents. Knowle West is a low-density estate – below 25 dwellings per hectare which is below the threshold to justify a regular bus service. There are few sources of local employment, public transport is poor, and the neighbourhood remains geographically isolated. The low population density makes it difficult to sustain shops and services, with many closing down or moving elsewhere, including the cinema, and swimming pool, and presently the library which is under threat of closure.

Nevertheless, the neighbourhood has a high level of housing need: 522 people in the Knowle West area are on HomeChoice, the Council's official housing waiting list. Knowle West represents 2.9% of the total population of Bristol, and 5.8% of people registered on HomeChoice are from the area – double its proportionate size.

9 Co-identification of the need

Over a year, in 2017, *We Can Make* brought together local people, artists, architects,

policy-makers, academics and industry professionals to collaborate between and beyond traditional professional and social silos. The aim was to understand the needs of people from *their perspective*, identify the nature of the problem, collate and map the assets and resources the community had available, and co-construct new citizen-led approaches to enable people to supply their own affordable housing at the point of need. This process maps on to the six learning design principles described above. The diagnosis of the issue of housing need was developed through a door-to-door-survey, narrative interviews, and semi-structured conversations at workshops and on doorsteps. Four types of unmet housing need were identified:

- **Down Shifters:** individuals or couples who want to stay in their neighbourhood but whose house is now too big for them and are looking for a smaller home. This could be because children have grown up and flown the nest, changing mobility needs, or a need to reduce costs in retirement.
- **New Shoots:** families where there is an urgent need for more space because children are growing up and seeking independence or are having offspring of their own, or caring responsibilities are expanding to include additional elderly or disabled family members.
- **Better Fits:** families where one or more member(s) is experiencing changing mobility and the family home needs to be adapted to enable them to stay close to their support networks.
- **Making Ends Meet:** individuals and families that need extra income or reducing their housing costs due to changing circumstances.

10 Co-diagnosis of barriers

The project team researched the assets and resources people had in the neighbourhood and found there was no shortage of change-ready attitude, know-how in construction and trade, spare capacity and land (Figure 2). The project also identified the barriers to citizens and their *communities* in applying some of these assets and resources to how people could go about supplying and securing their affordable housing at the point of need:

- Conventional strategies to access housing are reductively competitive. They either require people to divert ever more of their wages and savings to getting on a property ladder, where the bottom rungs are missing, or compel people to prove how ‘weak’ or ‘incapable’ they are in order to win eligibility for austerity rationed social housing. These dominant strategies can cause further damages, such as diverting capital to be locked in housing stock rather than other forms of investment that can circulate in the economy more productively, and

undermining an individual's sense of personal agency.

- An emerging alternative is the “third sector” – the civic or community sector. However, despite enabling legislation at national level and new forms of low-interest finance, the take-up so far has been slow – self-build and custom build account for just 7% of new homes delivered each year in the UK, compared to 80% in Austria and 60% in France.
- A significant barrier is caused by the deliberately veiled nature of the development process. Access to land, technical know-how, and financial resources continue to be controlled by professional interests and has disproportionate costs and barriers to entry; the current housing system is more often working against than supporting the civic or community approach. For example:
 - i) **Land:** most citizen-led schemes range from 1-10 homes, a size that is just too small and carries disproportionate transaction costs for most council site allocation and land disposal processes to bother with. At the same time the long-term social and economic impact of citizen-led housing struggles to make its added value count in a highest-sale-price-wins market. The result is that communities are often left with the most difficult sites, which commercial developers have rejected or are overly dependent on increasingly stretched local authorities as a route to get land at a discounted price.
 - ii) **Finance:** at each stage of the development process – from a lack of pre-planning development finance, the high cost of social investment, to a lack of capital reserves to accommodate construction cost overruns – risk and uncertainty accumulates. The high transaction costs of sticking together small pots of multiple funds each with different strings attached also creates substantial drag on community-led projects.
 - iii) **Technical know-how:** from planning permission to finding contractors, the process of making homes is dominated by costly professionals. The inequity this creates is clear – in Knowle West, planning applications are twice as likely to be rejected compared to wealthier neighbourhoods in Bristol.
 - iv) **No repeats:** Most community-led projects remain non-replicable and

the experience gained – often through years of ‘hard graft’ – by individual residents stays stuck to specific sites with few people wishing to repeat the experience. The result is high per- project overhead costs in terms of both time and money as each new amateur has to learn and master the process from scratch. The isolation of individual projects also means the citizen-led asset base – which might be able to fund the next project – fails to grow.

The systemized opaqueness and uncertainty mean many individuals and communities do not know what tools they need, cannot afford them anyway, and ultimately, do not have the faith that they can achieve the outcome they want – a safe, secure and affordable home. Using the terms of the layered framework of motivation, community-led housing was not an option in people’s existing goal constructs nor did they have the agency required to act upon this option. These findings informed the project’s next key task which was to co-design the collective tools that could help overcome these barriers.

Figure 2. Assets the Knowle West people and community had to utilise as captured by the WCM project.

11 Learning together to create an alternative approach

To lead the community through the transformative journey from a business-as-usual mindset to an innovative new approach, *We Can Make* utilised a mix of open research

and development tools and approaches to stimulate learning:

- Co-design of workshops which mixed residents, artists, and housing professionals to explore issues and ideas together in an open, learner-centred and non-hierarchical way;
- The involvement of artists to help open up learning conversations, invite new perspectives, translate between different communities and types of participant and create shared learning experiences, spaces, and new knowledge;
- Using visualisations to unravel and de-mystify complex issues and ideas and thus empower learning;
- Testing and re-testing emerging ideas and propositions with a wide range of stakeholders – including residents – learning and evaluating together as the project developed.

Figure 3. An illustrative graphic which helps citizens understand the community-led housing process from the perspective of a user whose need is Better Fits, which is one of the four types of needs identified in We Can Make.

Overall, *We Can Make* developed a different kind of user-led learning journey for people to find and realise ways to access affordable homes, attuned to their needs and resources, and created collective tools to support the individual journeys as a

process of learning. These processes were facilitated and captured using creative artefacts. For example, the project represented these individual learning journeys through illustrative graphics which help citizens understand the community-led housing process from the user perspective (Figure 3).

To make the community-led housing option an authentic experience and thus deepen the community learning, *We Can Make* then built a prototype home to pilot the development process from end to end, demonstrating with the community how some of the barriers could be overcome in practice. The pilot process involved the following elements:

- Identifying a micro-site next to a community centre;
- Development of community criteria for construction and design including local materials, local labour, sustainability, and affordability;
- Use of existing planning rules to permit the development;
- Employing local construction teams;
- Artists and local people designing and making fittings and furniture;
- A rapid prototype home built over 3 months;
- Local people experiencing and testing the home by staying in it.

The prototype home created an embodied space where people could see, feel and help make it happen, learning through experience. This is of critical importance in helping people incorporate this innovative approach of housing into their existing goal constructs; it demonstrated that a different way of imagining, making and accessing an affordable home is possible, as opposed to just a concept or topic for consultation. The community learning was deep and transformative through 'playing, making and doing' (Thomas & Brown, 2011).

12 Co-generation of community agency

A co-design approach was used throughout the research project with residents working alongside professionals to develop and test ideas, which inspired the community to develop their own 'agency' and become the developer. The prototype home has now had over 100 people staying in it, including locals and people from as far away as Berlin, San Francisco, and Melbourne. Local people stay for free to test out living in the home, and non-locals pay through AirBnB. The income is shared with a community centre who provided the micro-site, and in four months has contributed 10% of the centre's annual income.

KWMC also seeks funding and support to increase the resourcefulness of the

community and generate the ‘community agency.’ The We Can Make project has now been identified as a priority pathfinder project by Bristol City Council. The project has now secured support from Power to Change and the Nationwide Foundation to develop the collective tools, including a land assembly mechanism, financial tools, community design code, community supplier’s framework, and digital learning platform, to support the development and delivery of We Can Make in the pilot neighbourhood during 2018 and 2019.

13 Discussion

We Can Make’s achievements have arisen because sufficient people *became* motivated to work together to achieve a mutually beneficial common purpose. Such motivation is not a given; it is an outcome of a learning process that each individual participant and organisation goes through. The success of *We Can Make* is the result of the creative, purposeful and engaging approach to orchestrate the stakeholders’ collective learning journey, not simply following the script of the UrbanID Learning Framework presented in this paper. Nevertheless, the framework provides a useful working theory and set of design principles which explain the stakeholder engagement demonstrated in the *We Can Make* project and the quality of its outcomes.

First, establishment of a shared set of learning design principles helped to direct stakeholders’ attention to the intended shared goal. Framing the project’s co-production process – from identifying the problem, diagnosing the ‘blockers’, co-constructing and achieving an alternative goal – created a social environment that generated collaborative learning power, motivation and agency and therefore led to deep stakeholder engagement. Using the challenge themes as an analytical lens also prompted stakeholders to think systemically, leading to the development of a solution that is expected to have positive impact on most of the challenges themes. These links are presented in Table 1 below.

Second, there were three processes running in parallel throughout the *We Can Make* project:

- i) The identification of the problem and the ‘job to be done’;
- ii) The *behavioural processes* of co-production, including but not limited to those key tasks of collaborative learning discussed in section 3, which signpost the pathway forwards for stakeholders to navigate and so identify, collect and curate the necessary resource, data and information which will enable them ‘co-construct’ a solution and thus achieve their purpose – or ‘do the job’;

- iii) The intra- and inter-personal *learning processes*, as discussed in the layered framework of motivation: a meta-level, internal (and often invisible) element of co-production which is necessary to sustain engagement and lasting changes.

The behavioural processes and the learning processes, as we observed in the case study, were coupled like a double helix around the 'job to be done'. When both processes are facilitated and integrated appropriately around the 'job to be done' they are mutually reinforcing. Conversely, if either of the two processes is neglected or if they are managed separately as in isolated silos, it will limit the transformative potential of co-production. The job may still get done, but it will be less sustainable because the learning and knowledge co-production processes will not be embedded in the hearts and minds of the community and its stakeholders.

Table 1. The expected impact of We Can Make approach on the UrbanID exemplar challenge theses

Challenge theme	Community-led housing capability	Increase of local population density	Mobilisation of community resource
Mobility & accessibility	More variations of house designs to suit the needs of people with varied mobility and accessibility	Higher density makes it more cost and energy effective to run infrastructure services, including	
Health & happiness	User-centred development means the new houses better meet the quality required for a health and happiness	public transport, and other locally facilities, providing easier and less discriminated access to essential services for well-being.	Enhances collective and individual agency and relatedness
Equality & inclusion	WCM Financial Tools and Community Supplier Framework offers job and investment opportunity for local people to generate and retain value against the potential raise of house price as a result of development		Enabling much more diverse ways to contribute to and benefit from urban living than an exclusive mode of job earning and money spending
Carbon neutral city	The prototype home was built to high environmental standards (it is built of compressed straw); Developing carbon saving techniques and methods is part of the community learning process and will be embedded into the WCM assets		Increased resourcefulness means greater ability and willingness to adopt latest technologies which in general are more environment-friendly
Environment & ecology	Better use of land in existing residence reduces the development pressure on wild green space		

The third reflection is about the role that digital and visual artefacts and assets played in the *We Can Make* project. In a related community engagement study with Hunter Water Corporation³ in NSW, Australia, the components of a digital ‘always on’ community engagement platform have been developed based on the learning framework identified in this study. In its early stages, based on a data architecture which offers a ‘single view of the user’ it maps out the key tasks of the behavioural processes of co-production – or learning with the community - framing these around the ‘job to be done’, whilst identifying key trigger points for critical learning processes. The ‘job to be done’ in this example is to secure a resilient water future for the community – the content-neutral learning framework discussed here provides the ‘scaffolding’ (see Figure 4).

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Figure 4. The community engagement platform architecture developed by Learning Emergence Lab⁴

The importance of assets has been well understood by KWMC who have sought support and investment to advance their development of assets as part of the *learning infrastructure* of the community. The notion that this learning infrastructure has to include both learning facilitation services and physical and digital assets is consistent with the findings from a study of innovative business model for infrastructure (Crick, Huang, Godfrey, Taylor, & Carhart, 2017).

While it is widely accepted that co-production is incompatible with managerial control

³ <https://www.hunterwater.com.au/>

⁴ Learning Emergence Lab is the innovation engine of Learning Emergence Partners, a global collaborative of practitioners, data architects, business consultants and academics and a Community Interest Company. It is based in Scotland, UK.

exercised through a 'top-down' power structure (Meijer, 2016), it takes more than a simple reverse of power into a 'bottom-up' power structure to orchestrate effective co-production. What we have highlighted in this case study was the Living Lab as an organisation committed to the provision of a community service, which introduced mindful leadership in thought, action and relationships to energise and scaffold a co-production process which led to the emergence of a new social and industrial structure. This was the 'job' they set out to do: enabling the community to solve its housing problems. They did this through the intentional and visible use of (i) learning design principles in their mode of communications and relationships and (ii) the deployment of invited behavioural processes – key tasks that structured the journey from purpose to performance.

14 Conclusions

In the paper we presented the Learning Framework of the UrbanID project which was developed through participatory, user-led research. Through the case study of citizen-led housing, we illustrated the importance of framing and scaffolding co-production as a learning journey. We argued for the value of using learning journey design principles to facilitate the 'job to be done' through the interconnected *behavioural processes* and *learning processes* which empower stakeholder engagement in co-production. An additional insight emerging from our analysis is the critical role digital and visual artefacts and assets play in harnessing learning across the community over time. These insights led us to recognise that mindful leadership in thoughts and actions – leading to the provision of a community focused learning infrastructure - are important success factors for co-production in Living Labs.

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